

Supplementary material for

Losers and Winners: What People Think about Contested-Commodity Transactions

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Appendix A. The 14 transactions and our motivation

A.1. Verbatim transactions

Table 1

List of 14 transactions concerning a diverse array of goods and services.

Transactions	Good and service
Michael goes to Robert's car dealership. Michael pays Robert \$31,000 for a Ford F-150.	Car
Charlotte goes to Isabella's clothing store. She pays Isabella 35 dollars for a shirt.	Shirt
Brian goes to Jason's barbershop. Brian pays Jason \$25 for a haircut.	Haircut
Larry sees Shirley's advertisement in an art trading magazine. Larry buys Shirley's painting from Picasso for \$ 49,025 million.	Picasso
Melissa goes to George's travel agency. Melissa pays George \$5,141 for six nights in a luxury resort.	Luxury resort
Mia goes to Ava's plastic surgery clinic. Mia pays Ava \$5,483 for a nose plastic surgery (Rhinoplasty).	Rhinoplasty
Anna goes to the hospital with Rebecca. Anna pays Rebecca 110,000 dollars to have one of Rebecca's kidneys transplanted into her.	Kidney
Barbara goes to the maternity hospital with Julia. Barbara pays Julia 75,000 dollars to gestate a child and, after the birth, gives it to Barbara. Thus, Julia gives up her rights regarding the child, also known as surrogate motherhood.	Surrogate Maternity
John goes to Martha's house. John pays Martha \$260 for her to voluntarily have sex with him.	Sex work
Jim goes to the hospital with Oliver. Jim pays Oliver \$35 to have some of Oliver's blood plasma transfused into him.	Blood
Ryan visits Kathleen's orange tree farm. Ryan buys 3 acres of Kathleen's farmland for \$29.867	3 acres of orange trees
Liam connects with Olivia through an online housing portal. Liam buys Olivia's house for 428,700 dollars.	House
Kevin goes to Charles's family farm. Kevin pays Charles 750,000 dollars for selling him his entire farm.	Family farm
Henry is employed in Evelyn's brick factory as a warehouse worker. Henry sells his labor as a warehouse worker to Evelyn for \$16 per hour.	Warehouse Labor

A.2 Underlying motivations behind our selection of the 14 goods and services

First, we included three “mundane” goods and services (a haircut, a shirt, and a car) that were previously tested as “everyday” items by Johnson and colleagues (2021). These served as reference points to allow us to compare and replicate previous findings. Next, we selected four goods and services central to the anti-commodification debate, known for evoking buyer benefits perceptions, where buyers are often seen benefiting at sellers' expense. This group, consisting of kidneys, surrogate maternity, sex work, and blood, enabled us to analyze participants' evaluations of contested transactions. We chose a mix of high- and low-price items, including both familiar and less common transactions, to capture a broad range of perceptions.

Additionally, we included examples of goods and services where society often demands institutional support for sellers, like transactions involving labor and land, despite being part of regularized markets. To capture perceptions in this category, we included transactions involving warehouse labor, the sale of 3 acres of orange tree farmland, a family farm, and a house. Finally, we included three luxury goods—a Picasso painting, a week at a luxury resort, and rhinoplasty—to represent high-priced transactions that are generally distanced from moral controversies.

Appendix B. Demographics of Pre-Test and Main Study

B.1 General demographics

Table 1

Distribution of participants' evaluations.

	Variable	Mean	SD	Median
Pre-Test	Gender (0=Male)	0.64	0.48	
	Age	43.19	16.49	
	Income			USD 25,000 - USD 50,000
	Education			Completed secondary school
Main Study	Gender (0=Male)	0.61	0.49	
	Age	49.03	16.54	
	Econ_Edu (0=Yes)	0.70	0.46	
	Income			USD 25,000 - USD 50,000
	Education			Technical/vocational education

Note: The sample size of the Pre-Test is 242 participants, and the Main Study has 105 participants.

B.2. Ideological positions

Table 2

Participants' stances on surrogate maternity, abortion, and general political positioning.

	% of Pre-Test participants	% of Main Study participants
Legality of surrogate maternity		
It should be legal	60%	74%
It should be illegal	8%	2%
No preference	32%	24%
Legality of abortion		
Legal in all cases	26%	20%
Permitted up to a certain point of pregnancy	28%	35%
Illegal except for some exceptional cases	22%	24%
Illegal in all cases	8%	10%
No opinion	16%	10%
Political positioning		
Social justice	44%	41%
Conservative	17%	17%
Liberal	39%	42%

Appendix C. Participants' Responses to the Pre-Test and Main Study

C.1. Detailed responses to the Pre-Test

Table 1

Average participant's responses to the 7 statements (1 commodification + 6 control) concerning all tested goods and services.

Good and services	No answers	(1)		(2)		(3)		(4)		(5)		(6)		(7)	
		Mean	SD												
Car	103	0.45	0.30	0.62	0.25	0.63	0.25	0.69	0.26	0.70	0.24	0.72	0.22	0.73	0.25
Kidney	106	0.67	0.31	0.70	0.28	0.35	0.30	0.72	0.27	0.68	0.29	0.41	0.32	0.40	0.32
Orange tree farmland	105	0.65	0.26	0.69	0.25	0.63	0.24	0.57	0.26	0.68	0.24	0.73	0.22	0.56	0.29
Shirt	102	0.54	0.33	0.48	0.30	0.80	0.30	0.79	0.21	0.79	0.23	0.75	0.24	0.78	0.25
Surrogate maternity	105/108	0.80	0.23	0.81	0.21	0.52	0.28	0.62	0.27	0.53	0.28	0.39	0.30	0.40	0.30
Bearing a child	105	0.78	0.23	0.79	0.21	0.47	0.29	0.62	0.27	0.50	0.27	0.37	0.29	0.38	0.29
Raising a child	108	0.82	0.22	0.82	0.20	0.57	0.28	0.61	0.28	0.55	0.28	0.41	0.32	0.42	0.31
House	105	0.56	0.31	0.77	0.21	0.72	0.23	0.75	0.25	0.74	0.24	0.78	0.23	0.67	0.28
Sex work	104	0.66	0.26	0.66	0.26	0.45	0.28	0.53	N/A	0.40	0.29	0.43	0.29	0.59	0.30
Picasso	103	0.81	0.23	0.77	0.21	0.75	0.23	0.53	0.29	0.68	0.23	0.71	0.23	0.42	0.31
Haircut	107	0.46	0.31	0.58	0.28	0.51	0.28	0.74	0.26	0.71	0.25	0.73	0.24	0.68	0.27
Blood	106	0.68	0.28	0.69	0.26	0.39	0.30	0.75	0.25	0.68	0.28	0.55	0.28	0.49	0.30
Family farm	104	0.73	0.23	0.74	0.22	0.60	0.24	0.60	0.23	0.66	0.23	0.68	0.23	0.55	0.25
Warehouse Labor	103	0.68	0.25	0.71	0.21	0.47	0.26	0.52	0.27	0.49	0.28	0.46	0.28	0.45	0.29
Luxury resort	102	0.57	0.27	0.59	0.25	0.64	0.25	0.60	0.25	0.66	0.23	0.61	0.23	0.52	0.26
Rhinoplasty	103	0.40	0.29	0.48	0.29	0.48	0.31	0.49	0.29	0.50	0.30	0.53	0.30	0.45	0.30
Granola bars	99	0.48	0.31	0.47	0.29	0.35	0.28	0.63	0.29	0.63	0.29	0.66	0.29	0.58	0.30
Vehicle insurance	101	0.66	0.28	0.61	0.28	0.46	0.27	0.71	0.26	0.58	0.26	0.65	0.26	0.67	0.28
Cello recital	100	0.59	0.25	0.57	0.25	0.51	0.25	0.60	0.24	0.64	0.26	0.59	0.25	0.49	0.28
Movie on streaming	103	0.53	0.25	0.57	0.23	0.44	0.27	0.64	0.23	0.65	0.23	0.64	0.21	0.61	0.25
Chance games	103	0.45	0.30	0.62	0.25	0.63	0.25	0.69	0.26	0.70	0.24	0.72	0.22	0.73	0.25
Tarot readings	104	0.67	0.31	0.70	0.28	0.35	0.30	0.72	0.27	0.68	0.29	0.41	0.32	0.40	0.32

Note: (1) Is irreplaceable, (2) Has value beyond function, (3) Is a sign of status, (4) Everybody deserves having access to, (5) Is morally acceptable to gift, (6) Is morally acceptable to buy and sell, *i.e.*, not a contested commodities (CC), (7) Bought and sold daily. The initial answers on a 7-point Likert scale are re-scaled to a 0 to 1 scale. 1= strongly agree, and 0= strongly disagree. Although commercial surrogacy is a single transaction, it tracks two distinct moral components: the gestational act of bearing a child and the parental/custodial role of raising a child. We measure both and average them to capture overall attitudes toward surrogacy.

Table 2

Classification of commodities into CC or non-CC according to participants' answers.

Goods and services	Is it morally acceptable to buy and sell...?			
	Answers	Mean	SD	Categorization
Bearing a child	105	0.37	0.29	Contested
Surrogate maternity	105/108	0.39	0.31	Contested
Raising a child	108	0.41	0.32	Contested
Kidney	106	0.41	0.32	Contested

Sex work	104	0.43	0.29	Contested
Warehouse Labor	103	0.46	0.28	Contested
Tarot readings	104	0.51	0.31	Non-Contested
Chance games	103	0.52	0.26	Non-Contested
Rhinoplasty	103	0.53	0.32	Non-Contested
Blood	106	0.55	0.28	Non-Contested
Cello recital	100	0.59	0.25	Non-Contested
Luxury resort	102	0.61	0.23	Non-Contested
Movie on a streaming platform	103	0.64	0.21	Non-Contested
Vehicle insurance	101	0.64	0.26	Non-Contested
Granola bars	99	0.65	0.28	Non-Contested
Family farm	104	0.68	0.23	Non-Contested
Picasso painting	103	0.71	0.23	Non-Contested
Car	103	0.72	0.22	Non-Contested
Orange tree farmland	105	0.73	0.22	Non-Contested
Haircut	107	0.73	0.24	Non-Contested
Shirt	102	0.75	0.24	Non-Contested
Single-family house	105	0.78	0.23	Non-Contested

C.2. Detailed Responses to the Main Study

Table 3

Participants' combined evaluations were distributed to the two questions concerning the 14 transactions.

Buyer	Worse off	Worse off	Worse off	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Better off	Better off	Better off
Seller	Better off	Neutral	Worse off	Better off	Neutral	Worse off	Better off	Neutral	Worse off
Warehouse Labor	3%	1%	5%	18%	26%	2%	28%	9%	10%
Kidney	16%	4%	3%	7%	8%	0%	38%	4%	21%
Surrogate maternity	16%	5%	6%	3%	10%	1%	43%	8%	10%
Sex work	24%	2%	19%	13%	10%	2%	24%	2%	5%
Car	29%	2%	4%	6%	10%	2%	40%	2%	7%
Orange tree farm...	16%	0%	4%	7%	8%	0%	55%	5%	6%
Shirt	27%	3%	6%	10%	28%	0%	23%	3%	1%
House	23%	1%	3%	7%	9%	0%	50%	7%	1%
Picasso	30%	1%	5%	10%	9%	2%	41%	3%	1%
Haircut	17%	2%	4%	16%	26%	0%	30%	3%	2%
Blood	10%	3%	8%	7%	16%	0%	32%	17%	7%
Family farm	22%	1%	4%	8%	7%	1%	50%	4%	4%
Luxury resort	31%	2%	5%	11%	9%	2%	36%	4%	0%
Rhinoplasty	30%	3%	6%	15%	7%	0%	36%	3%	0%
Average	21%	2%	6%	10%	13%	1%	38%	5%	5%

Note: Better off = when the party is evaluated as improving their situation as a result of the transactions, neutral = when the party is evaluated as staying the same after the transactions, worse off = when the party is evaluated as worsening their situation as a result of the transaction.

Figure 1

Average participants' evaluations of contested and non-contested transactions.

Note: We report only the four welfare combinations relevant to our conjectures. The remaining combinations, where one or both parties are judged “the same as before”, are reported in Table 4.

Table 4

Participants' evaluations of buyers and sellers out of all evaluations.

	Buyer			Seller		
	Better off	Same as before	Worse off	Better off	Same as before	Worse off
Warehouse...	46%	46%	9%	49%	35%	16%
Kidney	63%	14%	23%	61%	15%	24%
Blood	56%	23%	21%	50%	36%	14%
Orange farm...	66%	14%	20%	78%	12%	10%
Maternity	60%	13%	27%	62%	22%	16%
Haircut	35%	42%	23%	64%	30%	6%
Family farm	58%	15%	27%	80%	11%	9%
Sex work	30%	25%	45%	61%	13%	26%
Car	49%	17%	34%	74%	13%	12%
House	58%	15%	27%	80%	16%	4%
Picasso	45%	20%	35%	80%	12%	8%
Shirt	27%	38%	35%	60%	33%	7%
Luxury resort	40%	22%	38%	79%	14%	7%
Rhinoplasty	39%	22%	39%	82%	12%	6%
Average	48% (SD=0.13)	23% (SD=0.11)	29% (SD=0.09)	69% (SD=0.20)	20% (SD=0.10)	12% (SD=0.07)

Appendix D. Benefit Index (BI)

D.1. BI

Table 1

Participants' average evaluations of buyers and sellers for the 14 transactions of the Main study.

	Goods and services	Buyers		Sellers		BI
		Average	SD	Average	SD	
CCs	Kidney	1.33	3.51	0.99	3.54	0.03
	Warehouse Labor	1.17	2.62	0.84	2.96	0.03
	Surrogate maternity	1.00	3.57	1.59	3.21	-0.06
	Sex work	-1.11	3.52	0.85	3.66	-0.20
	<i>Average</i>	<i>0.59 (SD=1.14)</i>		<i>1.06 (SD=0.35)</i>		<i>-0.04 (SD=0.10)</i>
Non-CCs	Blood Plasma	1.17	3.30	1.04	2.94	0.01
	Orange farm	1.11	3.22	2.02	2.75	-0.09
	Haircut	0.22	3.23	1.76	2.49	-0.15
	Cars	0.06	3.56	1.97	2.82	-0.19
	House	0.72	3.45	2.71	2.34	-0.20
	Family farm	0.91	3.49	2.91	2.78	-0.20
	Shirts	-0.66	3.17	1.58	2.46	-0.22
	Luxury resort	-0.44	3.54	2.34	2.58	-0.28
	Rhinoplasty	-0.49	3.46	2.46	2.50	-0.29
	Picasso	0.07	3.67	3.08	2.74	-0.30
<i>Average</i>	<i>0.26 (SD=0.68)</i>		<i>2.18 (SD=0.63)</i>		<i>-0.19 (SD=0.09)</i>	

Note: Scale of evaluations: worse than before = - 5, same as before = 0, better than before = + 5. BI = $((\mu \text{ buyer evaluations} - \mu \text{ seller evaluations})/\text{scale})$. BI = + 1 (*i.e.*, buyers absolutely better than sellers), 0 (*i.e.*, no difference in buyer and seller evaluations), - 1 (*i.e.*, sellers absolutely better than buyers).

Appendix E. Statistical analysis of participants' responses

E.1. Welch's t-test

Table 1

Welch's t-test on participants' evaluations of buyers and sellers when categorizing the goods and services according to the Pre-Test.

Goods and services seen as:	Buyer improves situation				Buyer worsens situation				Seller improves situation				Seller worsens situation			
	Mean	df	<i>t</i> Stat	<i>p</i> (2-tail)	Mean	df	<i>t</i> Stat	<i>p</i> (2-tail)	Mean	df	<i>t</i> Stat	<i>p</i> (2-tail)	Mean	df	<i>t</i> Stat	<i>p</i> (2-tail)
Irreplaceable	41.91	6	1.541	0.171	27.91	4	-0.731	0.507	67.27	4	-0.94	0.394	12.82	7	1.63	0.143
Replaceable	41.00				32.00				73.33				08.00			
Value beyond function	50.25	2	-2.552	0.148	27.42	6.30	-2.820	0.029**	68.17	1	-0.246	0.841	12.67	12	3.000	0.011**
No value beyond function	33.00				37.00				71.00				06.50			
Sign of status	47.25	11	-0.249	0.808	29.88	7	0.440	0.674	74.38	8	2.413	0.041*	7.88	6	-2.961	0.026
No sign of status	49.00				27.33				60.83				17.00			
Everybody deserves	48.69			n/a	28.00			n/a	67.54			n/a	12.23			n/a
Not everybody deserves	39.00				39.00				82.00				06.00			
Morally okay to gift	50.64	5	2.060	0.093*	28.18	2	-0.249	0.825	69.82	2	0.572	0.0614	10.64	2	-0.891	0.454
Not morally okay to gift	38.33				31.00				64.00				16.00			
Morally okay to exchange	29.90	5	-0.2989	0.785	29.90	7	0.503	0.644	72.70	10	3.121	0.011**	08.30	4	-4.360	0.013**
Not morally okay to exchange	26.60				26.00				58.25				20.50			
Frequently bought and sold	50.25	10	0.213	0.835	26.13	9.62	-0.514	0.168	0.921	8	0.921	0.374	09.38	10	-1.619	0.137
Not frequently bought and sold	48.20				30.27				0.347				15.40			

Note: We divide goods and services according to the average values of participants' evaluations; see Appendix C Table 1. Asterisks denote statistical significance at the 1% ($p < 0.01$ ***), 5% ($p < 0.05$ **), and 10% ($p < 0.1$ *) levels. Because only one item was categorized as “Not Everybody deserves,” we couldn't perform reliable estimations.

E.2. Multiple Linear Regression analysis

Table 2

Multiple Linear Regression analyzing the effects of demographic data on the Pre-Test and Main study.

	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Estimate	SE	95% CI		p
					LL	UL	
Pre-Test	Morally permissible to trade (non-CC)	Intercept	0.935	1.107	-1.245	3.115	.399
		Gender (0=Male)	-0.030	0.019	-0.068	0.007	.114
		Age	0.000	0.001	-0.001	0.001	.780
		Income (0=Lowest, 4=Highest)	0.001	0.009	-0.017	0.019	.915
		Education (0=None, 6=University education)	-0.016	0.006	-0.028	-0.005	.006***
		Social conservatism (0=Yes, 1= Not)	-0.061	0.025	-0.110	-0.012	.015
Main Study	Rejection of the mutual benefit	Intercept	9.702	2.484	4.774	14.631	.000
		Gender (0=Male)	0.646	0.797	-0.935	2.228	.419
		Age	0.058	0.024	0.011	0.106	.016**
		Income (0=Lowest, 4=Highest)	-0.825	0.395	-1.609	-0.042	.039**
		Education (0=None, 6=University education)	-0.477	0.371	-1.213	0.260	.202
		Econ_Edu (0=Yes)	-0.238	0.849	-1.924	1.448	.780
	Social conservatism (0=Yes, 1= Not)	-0.569	1.028	-2.609	1.471	.581	
	EI	Intercept	5.753	2.464	0.864	10.642	.022
		Gender (0=Male)	-0.096	0.791	-1.665	1.473	.903
		Age	-0.016	0.024	-0.063	0.031	.505
Income (0=Lowest, 4=Highest)		-0.406	0.392	-1.184	0.371	.302	
		Edu (0=None, 6=University education)	-0.300	0.368	-1.031	0.430	.417
		Econ_Edu (0=Yes)	-0.210	0.843	-1.882	1.462	.804
		Social conservatism (0=Yes, 1= Not)	-0.397	1.020	-2.420	1.627	.698

Note: Rejection of the mutual benefit concerns evaluations not signaling both parties as benefiting. EI: the measure of Exploitation Index. Asterisks denote statistical significance at the 1% ($p < 0.01$ ***), 5% ($p < 0.05$ **), and 10% ($p < 0.1$ *) levels.

Appendix F. Transcripts of the Pre-test and Main Study

F.1. Pre-test

We surveyed perceptions of 21 goods and services. Nevertheless, as our objective is to make conclusions on how seller benefits attitudes relate to people's moral perceptions of commodifying goods and services, we finally only analyzed the 14 goods and services for which we have data on zero-sum thinking and seller benefits.

The Pre-Test has 26 pages. Pages 3 to 22 are presented in random order. Participants have to answer all questions on one page before being able to advance (except for pages 24, 25, and 26). When displaying the statements on "sex work," we did not present the statement "everybody deserves to have access to" to avoid references to rape. To make the arguments semantically coherent, the framing of some goods and services has to be adapted. Mainly, for certain goods and services, the statements include "the experience of" to keep semantical coherence (i.e., a painting from Picasso, bearing a child, raising a child, chance games, tarot readings, a week in a luxury resort). Here we present a complete transcript of Pre-Test:

Pre-Test Page 1

Welcome to the study. We are interested in your opinion about economic transactions. It will take about 10 minutes to answer the questions. The study serves exclusively scientific purposes and is conducted by researchers from the XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX. If you have any questions about the study, please get in touch with XXXXXXXXXXXX (XXX@XXXXXX).

Your data will be anonymized, kept strictly confidential, and stored on secure platforms at XXXX. The data will also be made available for research purposes as "open data" on specific, internet-based information platforms. Data collection, processing, and storage follow the provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (DSGVO).

The simultaneous use of the language forms male, female, and diverse (m/f/d) is waived to improve readability. All personal designations apply equally to all genders.

We want to inform you that the following Study contains material that some audiences may consider sensitive or inappropriate. By clicking the yes button, you confirm that you are an 18+ year-old adult.

Do you participate voluntarily in this study?

-yes/no

Pre-Test Page 2

We will present you with different items. Please indicate your opinion on the following statements by choosing the most appropriate option.

Pre-Test Page 3

Granola bars are irreplaceable.

Granola bars have value beyond their functional purpose.

Granola bars are a signal of status.

Everyone deserves to have access to granola bars.

It is morally permissible to gift granola bars.

It is morally permissible to buy and sell granola bars.

In my social context, granola bars are bought and sold daily.

- I fully disagree/○/○/In between/○/○/I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Human kidneys are irreplaceable.
Human kidneys have value beyond their functional purpose.
Human kidneys are a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to human kidneys.
It is morally permissible to gift human kidneys.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell human kidneys.
In my social context, human kidneys are bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Three acres of orange tree farmland are irreplaceable.
Three acres of orange tree farmland have value beyond their functional purpose.
Three acres of orange tree farmland are a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to three acres of orange tree farmland.
It is morally permissible to gift three acres of orange tree farmland.
Buying and selling 3 acres of orange tree farmland is morally permissible.
In my social context, three acres of orange tree farmland are bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Shirts are irreplaceable.
Shirts have value beyond their functional purpose.
Shirts are a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to shirts.
It is morally permissible to gift shirts.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell shirts.
In my social context, shirts are bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of bearing a child is irreplaceable.
The experience of bearing and raising a child has value beyond its functional purpose.
The experience of bearing a child is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to the experience of bearing a child.
It is morally permissible to gift the experience of bearing a child.
Buying and selling the experience of bearing a child is morally permissible.
In my social context, the experience of bearing a child is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of raising a child is irreplaceable.
The experience of raising a child has value beyond its functional purpose.
The experience of raising a child is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to the experience of raising a child.
It is morally permissible to gift the experience of raising a child.
Buying and selling the experience of raising a child is morally permissible.
In my social context, the experience of raising a child is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

A house is irreplaceable.
A house has value beyond its functional purpose.
A house is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to a house.
It is morally permissible to gift a house.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell a house.
In my social context, a house is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Vehicle insurance is irreplaceable.
Vehicle insurance has value beyond its functional purpose.
Vehicle insurance is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to vehicle insurance.
It is morally permissible to gift vehicle insurance.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell vehicle insurance.
In my social context, vehicle insurance is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of voluntary sexual intercourse is irreplaceable.
The experience of voluntary sexual intercourse has value beyond its functional purpose.
The experience of voluntary sexual intercourse is a signal of status.
It is morally permissible to gift the experience of voluntary sexual intercourse.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell the experience of voluntary sexual intercourse.
In my social context, the experience of voluntary sexual intercourse is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 6 statements)

The experience of a cello recital is irreplaceable.

The experience of a cello recital has value beyond its functional purpose.

The experience of a cello recital is a signal of status.

Everyone deserves to have access to the experience of a cello recital.

It is morally permissible to gift the experience of a cello recital.

It is morally permissible to buy and sell the experience of a cello recital.

In my social context, the experience of a cello recital is bought and sold daily.

- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of a movie on a streaming platform is irreplaceable.

The experience of a movie on a streaming platform has value beyond its functional purpose.

The experience of a movie on a streaming platform is a signal of status.

Everyone deserves access to a movie's experience on a streaming platform.

It is morally permissible to gift the experience of a movie on a streaming platform.

It is morally permissible to buy and sell the experience of a movie on a streaming platform.

In my social context, the experience of a movie on a streaming platform is bought and sold daily.

- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

A painting by Picasso is irreplaceable.
A painting by Picasso has value beyond its functional purpose.
A painting by Picasso is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to a painting from Picasso.
It is morally permissible to gift a painting from Picasso.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell a painting from Picasso.
In my social context, a painting by Picasso is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

A haircut is irreplaceable.
A haircut has value beyond its functional purpose.
A haircut is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to a haircut.
It is morally permissible to gift a haircut.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell a haircut.
In my social context, a haircut is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Blood plasma is irreplaceable.
Blood plasma has value beyond its functional purpose.
Blood plasma is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to blood plasma.
It is morally permissible to gift blood plasma.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell blood plasma.
In my social context, blood plasma is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Family farms are irreplaceable.
Family farms have value beyond their functional purpose.
Family farms are a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to family farms.
It is morally permissible to gift family farms.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell family farms.
In my social context, family farms are bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The labor of a warehouse worker is irreplaceable.
The labor of a warehouse worker has value beyond its functional purpose.
The labor of a warehouse worker is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to the labor of a warehouse worker.
It is morally permissible to gift the labor of a warehouse worker.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell the labor of a warehouse worker.
In my social context, the labor of a warehouse worker is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of a week in a luxury resort is irreplaceable.
A week's experience in a luxury resort has value beyond its functional purpose.
A week's experience in a luxury resort is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves access to a week's experience in a luxury resort.
It is morally permissible to gift a week's experience in a luxury resort.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell a week's experience in a luxury resort.
In my social context, the experience of a week in a luxury resort is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Nose plastic surgery is irreplaceable.
Nose plastic surgery has value beyond its functional purpose.
Nose plastic surgery is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to nose plastic surgery.
It is morally permissible to gift nose plastic surgery.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell nose plastic surgery.
In my social context, nose plastic surgery is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

The experience of betting on chance games is irreplaceable.
The experience of betting on chance games has value beyond its functional purpose.
The experience of betting on chance games is a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to the experience of betting on chance games.
It is morally permissible to gift the experience of betting on chance games.
Buying and selling the experience of betting on chance games is morally permissible.
In my social context, the experience of betting on chance games is bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree//In between//I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

- Tarot readings are irreplaceable.
Tarot readings have value beyond their functional purpose.
Tarot readings are a signal of status.
Everyone deserves to have access to Tarot readings.
It is morally permissible to gift tarot readings.
It is morally permissible to buy and sell tarot readings.
In my social context, tarot readings are bought and sold daily.
- I fully disagree/○/○/In between/○/○/I fully agree (same options for all 7 statements)

Please choose the smiling emoji.

- 😊
- 😐
- 😡

- Finally, we are interested in some information about yourself (Not enforced)
Please indicate your gender:
-Male/Female/Other/Prefer not to say
Please mark your year of birth:
-1920 – 2004
What is your annual household income after tax?
Less than USD 25,000/USD 25,000 - USD 50,000/USD 50,000 - USD 100,000/USD 100,000- USD 150,000/More than USD 150,000
In what state do you reside?
-Alabama (1) ... Wyoming (50)
Please indicate your religious beliefs, if any:
- Christianity/Islam/Atheism, no religious beliefs/Hinduism/Buddhism/Taoism/Confucianism/ /Judaism/Other

- We are interested in your personal opinions:
Should it be legally permissible for one person to pay a woman for gestating a child and, after birth, give it permanently to the paying person (also known as surrogate motherhood)?
-Surrogated maternity should be legally permissible/Surrogated maternity should be forbidden/I don't have an opinion on the issue.
What is your opinion on abortion?
-Abortion should be legal for all cases/Abortion should be permitted up to a certain point in the pregnancy/Abortion should be illegal except for some exceptional cases/Abortion should be banned for all cases/ I don't have an opinion on the issue.
What is the highest educational level that you have attained?
-University-level education/Technical/vocational education beyond the secondary school level/Complete secondary school/Some secondary school/Complete primary school/Some primary school/No formal education

With which of the three following statements can you most closely identify?

-My heroes are people who have stood up for the underprivileged. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the oppression of women, minorities, and people experiencing poverty.

-My heroes are people who have stood up for Western values. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the assault on the moral virtues and traditions that are the foundation of our civilization.

-My heroes are people who have stood up for individual rights. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the government taking away people's ability to make their own choices.

F.2. Main Study

The main Study has 21 pages. Pages 3 to 16 are presented in random order. Participants have to answer all questions on one page before being able to advance (except on pages 18, 19, and 20). Here we present a complete transcript of the main Study:

Main Study Page 1

Welcome to the study on your opinion about economic transactions. It will take about 10 minutes to answer the questions. The study serves exclusively scientific purposes and is conducted by researchers from the XXXXXX. If you have any questions about the study, please get in touch with XXXXX (XXXXX@XXXXX).

Your data will be anonymized, kept strictly confidential, and stored on secure platforms at XXXXX. Data collection, processing, and storage follow the provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (DSGVO).

We want to inform you that the following Study contains material that some audiences may consider sensitive or inappropriate. By clicking the yes button, you confirm that you are an 18+ year-old adult.

Do you participate voluntarily in this study?

-yes/no

Main Study Page 2

You will now be presented with a series of different transactions. For each transaction, you will be asked whether each participant is better off, worse off, or the same relative to how they were before the transaction.

Main Study Page 3

Mia goes to Ava's plastic surgery clinic. Mia pays Ava \$5,483 for a nose plastic surgery (Rhinoplasty).

How well off do you think Mia is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

How well off do you think Ava is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

Kevin goes to Charles's family farm. Kevin pays \$1.125 million to Charles for selling him his entire farm.

How well off do you think Kevin is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Charles is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Ryan visits Kathleen's orange tree farm. Ryan buys 3 acres of Kathleen's farmland for \$29,867.

How well off do you think Ryan is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Kathleen is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Jim goes to the hospital with Oliver. Jim pays Oliver \$35 to have some of Oliver's blood plasma transfused into him.

How well off do you think Jim is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Oliver is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Brian goes to Jason's barbershop. Brian pays Jason \$25 for a haircut.

How well off do you think Brian is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Jason is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Liam connects with Olivia through an online housing portal. Liam buys Olivia's house for \$428,700.

How well off do you think Liam is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Olivia is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Michael goes to Robert's car dealership. Michael pays Robert \$31,000 for a Ford F-150.

How well off do you think Michael is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

How well off do you think Robert is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

Henry is employed in Evelyn's brick factory as a warehouse worker. Henry works at Evelyn's warehouse for \$16 per hour.

How well off do you think Henry is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

How well off do you think Evelyn is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

Larry bids for Shirley's art piece at an art auction event. Larry buys Shirley's painting by Picasso for \$9.546 million.

How well off do you think Larry is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

How well off do you think Shirley is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

Barbara goes to the maternity hospital with Julia. Barbara pays Julia \$75,000 to gestate a child, and after the birth, Julia gives it to Barbara. Thus, Julia gives up her rights regarding the child, also known as surrogate motherhood.

How well off do you think Barbara is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

How well off do you think Julia is?

-Worse than before / / / / / same as before / / / / better than before

Melissa goes to George's travel agency. Melissa pays George \$5,141 for six nights in a luxury resort.

How well off do you think Melissa is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think George is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

John goes to Martha's house. John pays Martha \$260 for her to voluntarily have sex with him.

How well off do you think John is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Martha is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Anna goes to the hospital with Rebecca. Anna pays Rebecca \$110,000 to have one of Rebecca's kidneys transplanted into her.

How well off do you think Anna is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Rebecca is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Charlotte goes to Isabella's clothing store. She pays Isabella \$35 for a shirt.

How well off do you think Charlotte is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

How well off do you think Isabella is?

-Worse than before /○/○/○/○/ same as before ○/○/○/○/better than before

Please indicate what this study was about:

- Evaluating various transactions and their effects on the transaction partners.
- The acceptance of GMO technologies for food production.
- The impact of social media consumption on self-esteem.
- Assessing the credibility of news outlets concerning their COVID-19 coverage.

Finally, we are interested in some information about yourself:

Please indicate your gender:

- Male/Female/Other/Prefer not to say

Please indicate your year of birth:

- 1920 – 2004

What is your annual household income after tax?

- Less than USD 25,000/USD 25,000 - USD 50,000/USD 50,000 - USD 100,000/USD 100,000 - USD 150,000/more than USD 150,000

In what state do you reside?

- Alabama ... Wyoming

Please indicate your religious beliefs, if any:

- Christianity/Islam/Atheism/Hinduism/Buddhism/Chinese traditional religions/Judaism/Other

We are interested in your personal opinions:

Should it be legally permissible for one person to pay a woman for gestating a child and, after birth, give it permanently to the paying person (also known as surrogate motherhood)?

- Surrogated maternity should be legally permissible/Surrogated maternity should be forbidden/I don't have an opinion on the issue

What is your opinion on abortion?

- Abortion should be legal for all cases/Abortion should be permitted up to a certain point in the pregnancy/Abortion should be illegal except for some exceptional cases/ Abortion should be banned for all cases/I don't have an opinion on the issue

What is your idea regarding transactions in agricultural land markets?

- Only the ones who work the land should own the land/the state should own all the land and lease it to whoever wants to work it/agricultural land markets should be free of any regulation/agricultural land markets should be regulated to avoid non-local and non-agricultural ownership/I don't have an opinion on the issue

What is the highest educational level that you have attained?

-University-level education /technical/vocational education beyond secondary school level complete secondary school/some secondary school/comprehensive primary school/ some primary school/no formal education

Did you receive any formal education in economics? (excluding high school)

-yes/no

With which of the three following statements can you most closely identify?

-My heroes are people who have stood up for the underprivileged. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the oppression of women, minorities, and people experiencing poverty.

-My heroes are people who have stood up for Western values. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the assault on the moral virtues and traditions that are the foundation of our civilization.

-My heroes are people who have stood up for individual rights. The people I cannot stand are the people who are indifferent to the government taking away people's ability to make their own choices.